

Histopathological Study of Nasal Masses- A 2-Year Study in a Tertiary Care Hospital

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Abstract:

Introduction: Nasal masses are common findings in the specimens received from the ENT department. [1] The incidence is 1-4% of the total population. Neoplasms of the sinuses and nasal cavity account for 0.2-0.8% of all carcinomas. The prevalence rate of nasal polyps is about 2%. They may be congenital, inflammatory, neoplastic, non-neoplastic, or traumatic.

Aim & Objectives: The main objectives were to study the various histopathological subtypes of nasal mass lesions and to classify the malignant lesions into different categories.

Methods: The study was carried out for two years. A total of 100 cases were included. It was a Descriptive observational cross-sectional study.

Result and Conclusion: The study included 100 cases of nasal mass lesions collected over 2 years (October 2022-October 2024). The study revealed male predominance, with a ratio of 2.12:1(68:32). The age ranged from 05 to 76 years with a mean age of 33.8 years. Unilateral involvement of the nasal cavity was found to be more common. The most common presenting complaint of the patient was found to be polypoidal nasal mass. 73 cases were found to be Non-neoplastic Lesions. Of the 27 Neoplastic Lesions, 14% cases were Benign while 13% were Malignant. Rhinosporidiosis (32%) and Inflammatory Nasal Polyp (32%) were the most common non-neoplastic lesions, Angiofibroma (4%) was the most common benign, and Undifferentiated carcinoma (7%) was the most common malignant neoplastic lesions.

Keywords: Nasal Mass Lesion, Benign, Malignant, Polypoidal, Descriptive.

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Introduction

The nose, a prominent facial feature, holds both aesthetic and functional significance, serving to filter, humidify, and adjust the temperature of inspired air. [6] The nasal cavity, paranasal sinuses, and nasopharynx form the functional unit of the nose and frequently present with both non-neoplastic and neoplastic lesions, affecting individuals across all age groups. Common symptoms include nasal blockage, discharge, smell disturbances, epistaxis, and facial swelling. [7]

Sinonasal masses, ranging from benign polyps to malignant tumors, are prevalent, with nasal polyps being the most common. These lesions pose diagnostic challenges due to their diverse etiologies, including allergies, infections, and environmental exposures. Neoplastic lesions, although comprising a small percentage of

carcinomas, often present significant clinical challenges due to their potential for local invasion and recurrence.[8]

The sinonasal region, lined by stratified squamous and pseudostratified columnar epithelium, plays a critical role in immunological defense, with various epithelial and glandular structures contributing to its function.[9] Notably, Rhinosporidiosis is endemic in specific regions like Chhattisgarh. [10]

Clinical features and imaging techniques help us in reaching a provisional diagnosis but histopathological examination remains the mainstay for making a final definitive diagnosis. [6] Histopathology has become indispensable in the timely diagnosis and treatment of these lesions.[11] This study aims to analyze the histopathological

patterns of nasal mass lesions and classify them into various subtypes, enhancing the understanding and management of these conditions.

Materials and Methods

The current research constituted a descriptive observational cross-sectional investigation conducted at a Department of Pathology Pt. J.N.M Medical College Raipur, Chhattisgarh, and associated Dr. B.R.A.M. Hospital, Raipur, Chhattisgarh, India from October 2022 to October 2024, following approval from the Institutional Ethics Committees (No./MC/Ethics/2023/350). 100 patients were taken which were clinically diagnosed and submitted for histopathological confirmation by 2 expert pathologists. Clinical details were taken from the proforma. The details of gross examination and hematoxylin and eosin-stained slides prepared from paraffin-embedded blocks were studied in details. The data were entered and interpreted in Microsoft Excel.

Results

The present descriptive observational cross-sectional study titled "Histopathological Spectrum of Nasal Mass Lesions" was conducted over 2 years in the Department of Pathology, Pt. J.N.M Medical College and associated Dr. B.R.A.M Hospital, Raipur. It consisted of 100 biopsies and

histopathological specimens clinically diagnosed as Nasal Mass Lesions in both the sexes of all age groups, coming to the histopathology laboratory and reviewed microscopically for histomorphological features. The Nasal Mass Lesions had a male predominance with a male-to-female ratio of 2.12:1 (Figure 5). The cases were found between the age group of 5 and 76 years with a maximum number of cases (24%) in the age range of 11-20 years (Figure 6). The mean age of the subjects was 33.8 years. Unilateral Nasal Mass Lesions (66%) were found to be more prevalent compared to Bilateral Nasal Mass Lesions (34%) (Figure 8). 73% of the cases were non-neoplastic lesions while 27% were Neoplastic lesions (Figure 9). In the neoplastic lesions, 14% of cases were found to be Benign while 13% were Malignant (Figure 10). Out of Non-neoplastic lesions, the most common were Inflammatory Nasal Polyp (32%) and Rhinosporidiosis (32%) (Table 1). Angiofibroma (4%) was the most common Benign neoplastic lesion (Table 2). Undifferentiated Carcinoma (7%) was the commonest Malignant Neoplastic lesion followed by MDSCC (2%). Malignant Epithelial Neoplasm, Sinonasal Carcinoma, Adenoid Cystic Carcinoma, and Alveolar Rhabdomyosarcoma each comprising of 1% of the cases (Table 3).

Figure 1: (H&E, 100x)-A sporangium filled with endospores (thick arrow) with surrounding shows infiltration with mixed inflammatory cell infiltrates

Figure 2: (PAS stain, 400x)- Positive for Mucormycosis (thick arrow)

Figure 3a: (H&E, 40x)- A case of Juvenile Nasopharyngeal Angiofibroma (also showing pseudostratified columnar epithelium-thick arrow) seen in a 12-year-old Male

Figure 3b: (H&E, 400x)- There are vesicular spaces and slit-like capillaries (thick arrow) with fibro-collagenous stroma and fibroblasts. Stroma is infiltrated with mixed inflammatory cell infiltrates

Figure 4a: (H&E, 100x) -A case of Alveolar Rhabdomyosarcoma in a 16-year-old Female

Figure 4b: (H&E, 400x)- Many rhabdomyoblasts (thick arrow) are noted and mitoses are also seen (thin arrow).

Figure 4c: (IHC-Desmin, 400x)- Positive for Rhabdomyosarcoma

Figure 5: Distribution of cases according to gender (n=100)

Age distribution of Nasal Mass Lesions

Figure 6: Age-wise distribution of cases (n=100)

Distribution of cases according to presenting complains

● Nasal bleed only ● Nasal Mass Only ● Nasal Mass with Nasal Bleed

Unilateral vs Bilateral Lesions

● Unilateral Lesions ● Bilateral Lesions

Figure 7 & 8: Distribution of cases according to presenting complaints (n=100) and Nature of Laterality (n=100)

Non-Neoplastic vs Neoplastic Lesions

Benign vs Malignant Lesions

Figure 9 & 10: Distribution of Non-Neoplastic vs Neoplastic and Benign vs Malignant Lesions:

Table 1: Histopathological types of Non-Neoplastic Lesions (n=73)

Types of Non-Neoplastic Lesions	No. of cases	Percentage
Rhinosporidiosis	32	44%
Inflammatory nasal polyp	32	44%
No Specific Pathology	5	7%
Mucormycosis	3	4%
Fungal nasal sinusitis	1	1%
Total	73	100%

Table 2: Histopathological Types of Benign Lesions (n=14)

Types of Benign Lesions	No. of cases	Percentage
Angiofibroma	4	29%
Antrochoanal polyp	3	21%
Inverted Papilloma	3	21%
Chronic Hypertrophic Polypoidal Rhinosinusitis	1	7%
Schneiderian Papilloma	1	7%
Lymphoid Hyperplasia of NALT	1	7%
Hemangioma	1	7%
Total	14	100%

Table 3: Histopathological types of Malignant Lesions (n=13)

Type of Malignant Lesions	No. of cases	Percentage
Malignant Epithelial Neoplasm	1	8%
MDSCC	2	15%
Sinonasal Carcinoma	1	8%
Undifferentiated Carcinoma	7	54%
Adenoid Cystic Carcinoma	1	8%
Alveolar Rhabdomyosarcoma	1	8%
Total	13	100%

Discussion

Polypoidal masses in the nasal cavity form a complex group of lesions with a wide spectrum of histopathologic features. While there are many non-neoplastic lesions including mainly the allergic and inflammatory ones, there are also a good number of neoplastic tumefactions in the nose and nasal sinuses. These lesions are often quite impossible to distinguish clinically and are labeled as “nasal polyps”. Histopathologic examination of such polypoidal masses shows a spectrum of lesions ranging from non-neoplastic ones to neoplastic tumours including benign and malignant neoplasms. [12] The observations of the present study were compared and correlated with recently published literature on certain relevant parameters.

A total of 100 cases were included in the study, of which 68 were male and 32 were female, with a male-to-female ratio of (2.12:1) displaying male predominance which was in concordance with the study by Aparna M. Kulkarni et al [13], which observed a male-to-female ratio was 2.16:1 considering its 117 cases (Figure 5). The study yielded results similar to studies by Dinesh Garg et al [14] and A. Lathi et al [8] which showed the male-to-female ratio of 1.98:1 and 1.55:1 respectively. All the studies including the present study indicate a unanimously present male predisposition for the lesions under consideration. This may be due to the increased prevalence of such disorder among the males or it may be simple reflection of overall higher male attendance in the hospital. [11]

The patient's age ranged from 5 years to 76 years and most of the cases were in the age group of 11-20 years (24%) (Figure 6). Our study was in concordance with studies by A. Lathi et al [8], S. S. Bist et al [15] and Nisha J. Parmar et al [16], all of whom reported maximum frequency in the 11-20 years age group. Hence the data suggests that nasal mass lesions show higher prevalence in a younger age group.

In our study, all 100 cases were between 5-76 years with a mean age of 33.8 years. This result was in concordance with studies -by A.A.K.A. Razek et al [17], S. S. Bist et al [15], and Rajat Sharma et al [11] with mean age of 39 years, 39.4 years and 31.5 years respectively. All the data from the

current and previous studies indicate a higher incidence of nasal mass lesions in the third decade of the general population.

A history of nasal bleed was present in 37% of patients (Figure 7) and 97% of the cases presented with nasal masses. This could be due to selection bias and a different geographical setting of the study.

Unilateral lesions (66%) were relatively more common than Bilateral lesions (34%) in our study (Figure 8). This was similar to studies, like S. S. Bist et al [15] with 74.55% unilaterality and Rajat Sharma et al [11] with 68% unilaterality.

Out of 73 non-neoplastic lesions, the most common were Inflammatory Nasal Polyp (32%) and Rhinosporidiosis (32%) in our study (Table 1). It was in definitive concordance with a study by Anjali Dasgupta et al [12] whose commonest Non-neoplastic lesion was Nasal polyp (32%). Similar studies were conducted by Zafar U et al [6], Dinesh Garg et al [14] and Janice Jaison et al [18], where the commonest non-neoplastic lesion was found to be Inflammatory Nasal Polyp. Our study observed a higher frequency of Rhinosporidiosis i.e. in 32% of cases which is discordant to the previously mentioned studies. However, a cross-sectional study conducted in a tertiary care hospital by Gupta R K et al [10] observed that Chhattisgarh is an endemic region for Rhinosporidiosis infection in Central India. This high prevalence can be explained by the suitable hot tropical environment as well as the social practice of common bathing of the public with animals outdoors, mainly in ponds and rivers. Another case study conducted by Arias A F et al [19] stated that Rhinosporidiosis is caused by *Rhinosporidium seeberi*, a pathogen currently considered a fungus-like parasite of the eukaryotic group Mesomycetozoa. It is usually a benign condition, with slow growth of polypoid lesions, with involvement of the nose, nasopharynx, or eyes. The clinical characteristics of a painless, friable, polypoid mass, usually unilateral, can guide the diagnosis, but the gold standard for diagnosis is histopathological findings.

73% of cases were Non-neoplastic lesions while 27% were Neoplastic lesions (Figure 9). Our observations are similar to studies conducted by A. Lathi et al [8] (showing 71.43% Non-neoplastic

cases and 28.57% Neoplastic cases) and Janice Jaison et al [18] (with 74.04% Non-neoplastic cases and 28.57% Neoplastic cases).

Angiofibroma (4%) was the most common Benign neoplastic lesion (Table 2). It was in concordance with the studies conducted by Zafar U et al [6], A.A.K.A. Razek et al [17], and S. S. Bist et al [15].

Undifferentiated Carcinoma was the commonest Malignant Neoplastic lesion accounting for 7% of cases (Table 3). This result is in concordance with a study conducted by Kalpana Kumari et al [20]. Squamous Cell Carcinoma (SCC) was the second most common type of Malignant lesion in our study with 2% of cases. Concerning the frequency of SCC Lesions, our study is concordant with a study conducted by Nisha J. Parmar et al [16]. Hence, it was similar to studies conducted by Dinesh Garg et al [14] and K Pushpalatha et al [21]. Malignant Epithelial Neoplasm constituted 1% of cases in our study. Sinonasal Carcinoma comprised 1% of the cases and it was similar to the study conducted by Kapil Dua et al [22]. 1% cases of Adenoid Cystic Carcinoma were observed in our study which was in concordance with a study conducted by Kapil Dua et al [22]. It was also found similar to studies by A.A.K.A. Razek et al [17] and Aparna M. Kulkarni et al [13]. Alveolar Rhabdomyosarcoma comprised 1% of cases and it was similar to studies conducted by A.A.K.A. Razek et al [17] and Parajuli S et al [23]. Hence it did not show definitive concordance with any study.

14% were Benign while 13% were Malignant in our entire study (Figure 10). It produced results concordant with similar studies conducted by Kalpana Kumari et al [20], Janice Jaison et al [18], and Nisha J. Parmar et al [16].

The true nasal polyps are tumour-like non-neoplastic polypoidal masses arising from the nasal cavity and sinuses. Two types are encountered- one is associated with nasal allergy with numerous eosinophilic infiltration of the stroma on histopathology and the other found in relation to chronic naso-sinusoidal infections termed the inflammatory or granulomatous polyp. [12] The exact pathogenesis of the nasal polyps is not known, but they are strongly associated with allergy, asthma, aspirin sensitivity, and infection.[14]

Angiofibroma occurs predominantly in adult males. Angiofibromas are characteristic lesions with blood spaces separated by excessive fibrous tissue occurring chiefly in adolescent males. [12]

In our study Undifferentiated carcinoma was found to be seen in extremes of age with a male predominance. Undifferentiated carcinoma is an uncommon, highly aggressive, and

clinicopathologically distinctive carcinoma of uncertain histogenesis. The etiology of sinonasal undifferentiated carcinomas is unknown. There may be an association with cigarette smoking or a previous history of radiation therapy. It is believed to originate from Schneiderian epithelium or from the nasal ectoderm of the paranasal sinuses. It typically presents as a rapidly enlarging tumour mass involving multiple (sinonasal tract) sites, often with evidence of extension beyond the anatomic confines of the sinonasal tract. Given the undifferentiated nature of this malignancy, however, immunohistochemical analysis is extremely helpful. With the use of a panel of markers, positive staining for neuron-specific enolase and chromogranin, cytokeratins 7, 8 and 19, nonreactive to S-100 and non-expression of vimentin. These findings suggest that the tumour is of epithelial origin and lacks any evidence of neuroendocrine, muscle, melanocyte or leukocyte differentiation. This allows proper classification of the tumour as a Sinonasal Undifferentiated Carcinoma- a malignant tumour of the sinus (sinonasal) that is of epithelial origin (carcinoma) but lacks evidence of keratin production (undifferentiated). [24]

Squamous Cell Carcinoma histologically show tumour cells arranged in nests, masses or groups with evidence of squamous differentiation in the form of intracellular keratin, intercellular bridges and extracellular keratin pearls. [14] Adenoid cystic carcinoma most commonly arises in the major and minor salivary glands. Tumours of minor salivary gland origin occur in the nose as well as nasal sinuses, large majority of such tumours are malignant and adenoid cystic carcinoma is the most common type.[12] Alveolar Rhabdomyosarcoma are rare tumour of connective tissue origin but can present as primary neoplasm of the nose and paranasal sinuses.[12] Alveolar Rhabdomyosarcoma of the head and neck are very rare in adults. [23]

As the initiating cause of the nasal polyps is still not clear, it is essential to understand the Histomorphological Spectrum of Nasal Mass Lesions. Our study attempted to add further knowledge about the histopathology of nasal mass lesions. [21]

Conclusion

Nasal Mass Lesions are a commonly faced challenge among ENT OPDs throughout India. They always present a diagnostic challenge for the clinician as well as the Pathologist due to various clinical presentations and overlapping histopathological and clinical features. Our study is an attempt to study histomorphological features of Nasal Mass Lesions as histopathological examination is still the gold standard to establish

the diagnosis despite the emergence of newer techniques like Radiological studies and Nasal Endoscopy. Definitive diagnosis requires histopathological examination, and most of the lesions are either inaccessible for fine needle aspiration cytology (FNAC) or FNAC is not recommended because of fear of brisk hemorrhage.[6] These Lesions can be classified into different subgroups based on light microscopy. A definite and prompt diagnosis can be instrumental for early diagnosis and treatment resulting in immediate alleviation of symptoms. A definite diagnosis can warrant targeted treatment leading to the reduction of recurrence and remission of various lesions.

The study's limitations were our inability to perform Immunohistochemistry in our cases requiring Immunohistochemistry to confirm diagnosis, especially for malignant cases .

During the study, it was found that many of the specimens received at the histopathological laboratory were poorly preserved and could not be analyzed, in our opinion better protocols should be in place that help the surgeons in adequately preserving the samples.

We also found that various types of lesions have varying degrees of recurrences which need to be addressed with proper follow-up. A comprehensive histopathological examination of the lesions can help in proper diagnosis and early management of recurrence in such cases thereby improving patient comfort.

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